

EXISTENCE OF SOME TRANSIENT HYDRATES

By BHOLANATH GHOSH

The presence of a large number of transient salt hydrates, with or without catalysts has been detected during the process of thermal dehydration of the hydrated salts by a differential thermocouple method.

It has been shown by the author (*J Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1941, 18, 472) that the composition of hydrates can be fixed from a measurement of velocities of hydration and dehydration. Accurate experimentation shows that some hydrates, not otherwise traced, may appear occasionally in presence of catalysts. The nature of the nuclei developed in crystals during the process of dehydration has also been studied microscopically by the freeze-out method. The purpose of this paper is simply to trace some transient hydrates by a simple dehydration experiment, based on a differential thermo e.m.f. measurement principle. Such a method has already been used by Taylor and Klug (*J. Chem. Phys.*, 1936, 4, 601) who found by differential thermo e.m.f. method a hydrate of composition $\text{CuSO}_4 \cdot 4\text{H}_2\text{O}$ to appear during dehydration of copper sulphate pentahydrate which cannot be traced by any other method. Besides this, they give informations as regards the temperature at which water molecules in the crystal lattice change over from oscillatory to rotational state.

EXPERIMENTAL

The hydrate to be investigated was put in a small bucket hung from a spring balance suspended in vacuum. Weight of the salt can thus be obtained by measurement of the distance between two fiducial marks of the balance. One junction of a thermocouple was inserted in the hydrate and the other junction kept in a bucket containing sodium chloride and the two junctions connected differentially. The two buckets were then simultaneously heated by keeping them together side by side in a common furnace whose temperature was slowly raised, with time. A galvanometer was connected in the thermocouple circuit to read the e.m.f. developed. Sudden changes in the deflection of the galvanometer indicate the formation of some hydrates transient (unstable) or stable. It may also indicate some sudden intrinsic changes in the nature of crystal lattice vibration or rotation. An extra thermocouple read the temperature of the furnace, to indicate the temperature at which the change took place. One junction of a supplementary thermocouple was kept embedded in the hydrate, the other junction being in ice, for direct determination of the temperature of the salt, as distinct from the temperature of the environment. All the thermocouples were made of very fine wires. The spring balance read the mass of the salt at the instant, where sudden changes were occurring in the e.m.f. of the differential couple. Sometimes the buckets were surrounded inside the furnace by freezing mixture kept in some suitable vessel. The heating current in the furnace was then put on, and increased slowly and the changes in mass and e.m.f. were measured as a function of time. This is necessary for studying low temperature changes in the hydrates during dehydration.

TABLE I

w stands for H₂O and T for temp. in °C at which a particular hydrate or structure is being formed (given in bracket). s, m, and l indicate respectively strong, medium and small.

Hydrated salt.	Catalyst.	Hydrates and the corresponding w and T.	Others' data.	Author's data	Others' value.
CaCO ₃ , 5H ₂ O	—	4½w(8s); 4½w(9s); 4w(9s) 3w(10s); 3w(11s); w(11s)	4w(9s); 3w(10s) (Gibbs, loc. cit.); w(11s) (Tyler & King, loc. cit.)	3s°(s); 3s°7(0); 5s(θ)	29, 35, 53, 7
CaCO ₃ , 5H ₂ O	Gold dust	4w(9s); 3½w(9s); 3w(10s); 2½w(11s); w(11s); ½w(13s)	—	3s°(0); 2s(θ); 3s(θ); 47(0)	—
BeSO ₄ , 7H ₂ O	—	6w(0); 3w(1s); 4½w(4s); 4w(57) 3w(8s); 2½w(12s); 2½w(13s); 1w(18s)	6w(0) 4w(3s); 2w(11s); 1w(16s); ow(23s) (Parsons, <i>J. Amer. Chem. Soc.</i> , 1904, 26, 731. <i>Science</i> , 1906, 23, 402)	-10(θ); -3(0); 7(m); 21(0)	—
TeSO ₄ , 7H ₂ O	Sodium silicate	6w(-2°); 5w(1s); 4½w(5s); 4w(57); 3w(6s); 2w(12s); 1½w(13s); 1w(18s); ½w(20s); ow(26s)	—	-14(0); -10(θ); -4(0); +10(m); 27(m)	—
Zn Cl ₂ , 4H ₂ O	—	3½w(-3s); 2½w(-5); 2w(10); 1½w(26); 1w(6s); ½w(11s); ow(18s)	4w; 3w; 2½w; 1w; ½w; (Mylina & Dietz, <i>Z. anorg. Chem.</i> , 1905, 45, 217)	-26(θ); -14(0); +16(θ); +37(m)	—
Zn Cl ₂ , 4H ₂ O	Cu dust	3½w(-3s); 3w(-2s); 2½w(-1s); 2w(12s); 1½w(26); 1w(6s); ½w(12s); ow(18s)	—	-24(θ); -2s(0); -12(θ); 15(m); 39(0)	—
ZnSO ₄ , 6H ₂ O	—	5½w(21); 5w(28); 4w(8s); 3w(9s); 2w(18s); 1w(14s); ½w(27s)	6w, 5w, 3½w, 3w, 2w, 1w (Mellor, <i>Treatise on Inorganic Chemistry</i> , Vol. II)	0(θ); 14(0), 19(θ); 37(0); 56(m)	—
ZnSO ₄ , 6H ₂ O	Sodium phosphate	5½w(2s); 5w(4s); 4½w(7s); 4w(8s); 3½w(8s); 3w(9s); 2½w(10s); 2w(12s); 1½w(13s); 1w(14s); ½w(18s)	—	-4(θ); +7(0); 15(θ); 21(0); 36(θ); 5s(0); 58(m)	—

DISCUSSION

The data obtained have been represented in Table I. From inspection of the table it is evident that a large number of transient hydrates are formed, which are dynamically stable but which cannot be traced or isolated by any experiment of the static type. Besides these, a large number of changes in lattice vibrations have also been traced the nature of which seems to be unexplored as yet. The study of phase diagram of the ternary system consisting of the salt in question in presence of a second catalytic salt and water is likely to throw more light on this problem. The transient hydrates formed by the presence of finely divided metal, seems to be controlled by adsorption phenomena. In order that the catalysts may act effectively, the salt must be powdered very finely, and mixed intimately so that field of force of the metallic surface may influence the crystal formation in an effective manner.

The formation of these transient structures is perhaps first induced at the surface of the salts by the presence of foreign catalyst, which produces subsequently deeper changes in the salts undergoing dehydration and these seem to be transmitted to the interior so that the whole crystal system undergoes transient modifications and a new type of crystal structure is built up for a certain duration of time.

PHYSICAL LABORATORY,
SCIENCE COLLEGE, PATNA.

Received November 13, 1942.
